

Does Financial Literacy Influence Investment ? A Systematic Literature Review

Yatmoko Baroto

State University of Jakarta – Indonesia

Correspondence Author : yatmoko.baroto@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

Research Objectives: The primary goal of this study is to investigate the influence of financial literacy on individuals' inclination towards investment and their subsequent decision-making processes. By analyzing existing academic literature, our aim is to uncover patterns and trends in the correlation between financial literacy and investment behavior.

Research Methodology: To accomplish our objectives, we employ the Systematic Literature Review methodology, specifically implementing the PRISMA approach. This methodological framework facilitates a thorough and structured examination of pertinent articles sourced from the Scopus database. Through strict adherence to inclusion and exclusion criteria, we ensure the selection of high-quality scholarly works that significantly contribute to our investigation.

Originality: Previous research has not explored the connection between financial literacy and investment behavior within the context of the Scopus database. This database is renowned for housing reputable scholarly articles and is highly regarded in academia.

Contribution: This study makes a valuable contribution to the scholarly discussion on financial literacy by offering insights derived from a systematic analysis of relevant literature. By synthesizing findings from diverse scholarly sources, our aim is to enhance understanding of how financial literacy influences individual investment decisions. Additionally, our study has practical implications for investors, providing them with valuable guidance in navigating investment opportunities.

Keywords : Financial , Financial Literacy, Investment, systematic literature review, PRISMA methodology

INTRODUCTION

Financial literacy plays a crucial role in influencing the financial decisions and outcomes of investors. It includes various financial behaviors, attitudes, skills, knowledge, and awareness that collectively shape individuals' financial choices and achievements. (Khan et al., 2021). According to the Organization for Economic Co-operation and Development, financial literacy involves comprehending financial skills, risks, and concepts as well as having the motivation and confidence to make informed decisions that improve both individual and societal financial security(Lusardi, 2019). As financial markets become increasingly complex and individuals have more responsibilities for managing their own finances, the importance of financial literacy cannot be overstated.

Previous studies have demonstrated that a lack of financial literacy among investors can result in poor financial decision-making, personal bankruptcy, and market downturns (Arora & Chakraborty, 2023). Conversely, investors with higher levels of financial literacy are more inclined to make sound financial decisions and may also anticipate greater returns on their retirement investments. Effective financial planning is deemed crucial for managing risks and preventing financial losses.

Therefore, bolstering the financial literacy of investors is paramount in enhancing financial decision-making, minimizing risks, and ultimately realizing more favorable financial outcomes. (Khan et al., 2021). The lack of financial literacy (Ahmad et al., 2022). Seeking help from unbiased financial advisors can help mitigate the negative impacts of financial illiteracy. Research by Kramer (2016) revealed a significant negative relationship between self-assessed financial literacy and seeking expert advice(Chauhan & Dey, 2020).

Furthermore, Lotto et al. (2020) suggested that improving financial literacy can reduce the disposition effect, leading to better investment decisions(Lotto, 2020). Individuals with higher financial literacy tend to exhibit attributes such as patience, ability, or talent that contribute to making sound financial decisions ([Mwathi, 2017](#)). Research has also shown that individuals with good financial literacy are more likely to have smaller and more predictable losses on loans due to having clear plans for loan management and repayment compared to less financially literate individuals.

This study aims to review the impact of financial literacy on investors and explore the relationship between them, focusing on the tools, techniques, variables, findings, and practical implications of financial literacy. By identifying the outcomes of financial literacy research, this study aims to contribute valuable insights to both practitioners and the academic community (Bayar et al., 2020) Aim of this study is to answer research question mentioned below :

RQ1: What methods and approaches have been utilized in prior financial literacy literature?

RQ2: What factors, results, and real-world applications have emerged from studies on financial literacy?

RQ3: What are the key results and implications derived from research in the field of financial literacy?

METHOD AND MATERIAL

The Systematic Literature Review methodology, initially proposed by (Denyer & Tranfield, 2009), makes use of the PRISMA tool. This tool incorporates a four-stage flowchart developed by Moher et al. in 2009. The PRISMA tool is organized into three main steps: Review Planning, Review Conducting, and Results Reporting (Yuwono et al., 2023). The review process will involve a thorough search of relevant literature using Scopus databases. The inclusion criteria for the literature search will focus on studies that examine the relationship between financial literacy and investors' financial decision-making, as well as the impact of financial literacy on investment outcomes. The review process will also consider studies that propose methods for improving financial literacy among investors.

One key advantage of the PRISMA protocol is its ability to streamline the process of searching for articles related to a specific subject area, ultimately saving time. In the field of finance, where comprehensive lists for conducting systematic literature reviews may be lacking, researchers often rely on existing descriptive protocols to guide their review process. The application of the PRISMA protocol in this study will ensure a systematic and

comprehensive review of the literature on financial literacy and its effects on investor behavior and outcomes, providing a solid foundation for the analysis and synthesis of the available research (Hastings et al., 2012).

The systematic literature review process requires thorough planning, carrying out the review, and presenting the results in a structured manner (Lusardi, 2019). The final search for relevant literature was completed on May 11, 2022, with the stages of the review being categorized accordingly.

Keywords utilized in the systematic review of literature include "Financial AND Literature AND Investment" as indicated in Table 1.

Tabel.1 Keywords applied during the systematic literature review process

Database	Keywords
Scopus	Financial AND Literature AND Investment

The researchers conducted a systematic literature review on financial literacy and investment, using the keywords "investors" and "financial literacy". The all operator was used to retrieve a broader range of articles and studies related to financial literacy.

Scopus, a widely recognized database known for its comprehensive compilation of peer-reviewed literature in diverse fields, was utilized by the researchers. This database contributes to reducing bias and improving the transparency of the study protocol, as suggested by Briner and Denyer.

The systematic literature review focused on articles published in academic journals and written in English to maintain the rigor and relevance of the included literature. The study outlines detailed criteria for including or excluding papers, as specified in Table 2.

Table 2. Inclusion and Exclusion Criteria

Criteria	Inclusion	Exclusion
Access	Access Open Access	Closed Access Documents
Document Type	Articles	Book chapters, Reviews, Conference papers, Books, Conference proceedings, and book series
Source Type	Journals	Books, Editorials, Letters, Short surveys
Language	English	Non-English Languages
Period	2014 - 2024	2014 and Earlier
Subject Area	Economics, Finance, Accounting, Business, Other Disciplines	Others

Identification of studies through databases and registrations, as well as other methods related to finance and investment. A total of 72 records were identified through the Scopus database, but some of them were removed before the screening process. After the screening process, 32 studies were included in the review, while 25 reports could not be retrieved. No studies from other sources were included in the review.

Review Conducting

In conducting the review, as suggested by (Denyer & Tranfield, 2009), the systematic literature review should encompass a comprehensive approach, involving two key phases: Descriptive analysis and Main analysis. The Descriptive analysis focuses on gathering information such as publication trends by year, journal sources, and author contributions. This data collection aids in identifying patterns and trends within the research domain. Subsequently, the Main analysis is employed to organize and collect information systematically to fulfill the study's objectives. This phase commences with a thorough examination of the full-text papers to familiarize oneself with the content. Following this, the researcher categorizes the areas of study based on the research questions and objectives. The gathered information is then recorded, integrated, and structured accordingly.

Result Reporting

In the final stage of result reporting, the researcher verifies the consistency of the Systematic Literature Review and elucidates the overall findings. Through an analytical process, the researcher identifies the main findings and trends by aligning them with the research objectives. This step ensures that the outcomes of the study are accurately presented and contribute to the understanding of the research area.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Historical Publication Trend by Year :

From Chart no. 1 : The research trend shows a steady increase in the number of articles published each year from 2009 to 2024. The data indicates a gradual growth in research output over the years, with fluctuations in the number of articles published annually. A notable surge in the number of articles is observed in 2023, with 17 articles, reaching a peak, followed by a slight decrease to 9 articles in 2024. This trend suggests a growing interest and engagement in research activities within the specified period, with a significant rise in research productivity towards the later years.

Table 3. Journal and Number of Article

No.	Journal	Number of Article
1	journal of Business Strategy and the Environment	1
2	Journal of Business Ethics	1
3	Journal of Environment, Development and Sustainability	1
4	Journal of Letters in Spatial and Resource Sciences	1
5	Journal of Borsa Istanbul Review	2
6	Journal of International Review of Financial Analysis	1
7	Journal of Cleaner Production	1
8	Journal of Environmental Management	1
9	Journal of Open Innovation: Technology, Market, and Complexity	1
10	Resources Policy	1
11	Research in International Business and Finance	1

12	Humanities and Social Sciences Communications	1
13	Journal of Humanities and Social Sciences Communications	1
14	Journal of Applied Economics	1
15	Journal of Cogent Business & Management	1
16	Journal of Asian Review of Accounting	1
17	The International Journal of Business in Society	1
18	Corporate Governance: The International Journal of Business in Society	1
19	European Business Review Journal	1
20	European Journal of Training and Development	1
21	International Journal of Energy Sector Management	1
22	International Journal of Productivity and Performance Management	1
23	Journal of Applied Accounting Research	1
24	Journal of Indian Business Research	1
25	Journal of Knowledge Management	1
26	Journal of Public Budgeting, Accounting & Financial Management	1
27	Journal of Property Investment & Finance	1
28	IEEE Transactions on Engineering Management Journal	1
29	Sustainability Journal	9
Total of Articles		32

Among the 32 articles delineated in the table 3, they are dispersed across 29 distinct journals. Notably, the journal "Sustainability" emerges with a prevalence of 9 articles, whereas the majority of journals exhibit singular article representation. This distribution underscores the diverse thematic spectrum encapsulated by these scholarly publications.

Table 4. Analysis Method of the Articles

No.	Authors	Country	Methods Used	number of respondents
1	(Oehler et al., 2024)	Japan.	- Structural equation modeling (SEM) was used for data analysis. - Likert scaling technique was used to develop the questionnaire.	4962 respondents
2	(Xiao et al., 2022)	Japan.	- Structural equation modeling (SEM) was used for data analysis. - Likert scaling technique was used to develop the questionnaire.	4,000 respondents
3	(Cupák et al., 2022)	Japan.	- Structural equation modeling (SEM) was used for data analysis. - Likert scaling technique was used to develop the questionnaire.	- The research does not specify the exact number of respondents.
4	(Cupák et al., 2022)	Taiwan	- Structural equation modeling (SEM) was used for data analysis. - Likert scaling technique was used to develop the questionnaire.	1,215 respondents
5	Jiang et al.	Japan.	- Structural equation modeling (SEM) was used for data analysis. - Likert scaling technique was used to develop the questionnaire.	30,051 respondents
6	(Xiao et al., 2022)	China	- Structural equation modeling (SEM) was used for data analysis. - Likert scaling technique was used to develop the questionnaire.	3799 respondents
7	(Barthel & Lei, 2021)	USA	- Structural equation modeling (SEM) was used for data analysis. - Likert scaling technique was used to develop the questionnaire.	400 respondents
8	(Mouna & Anis, 2017)	Tunisia	- Structural equation modeling (SEM) was used for data analysis. - Likert scaling technique was used to develop the questionnaire.	250 respondents
9	(Ullah et al., 2024)	Pakistan	- Structural equation modeling (SEM) was used for data analysis. - Likert scaling technique was used to develop the questionnaire.	388 respondents

10	(Jariwala, 2015)	India	- Structural equation modeling (SEM) was used for data analysis. - Likert scaling technique was used to develop the questionnaire.	385 respondents
11	(Oppong et al., 2023)	Japan	- Structural equation modeling (SEM) was used for data analysis. - Likert scaling technique was used to develop the questionnaire.	- 400 respondents
12	(Anderson & Robinson, 2022)	USA	- Structural equation modeling (SEM) was used for data analysis. - Likert scaling technique was used to develop the questionnaire.	4,257. respondents
13	(Adil et al., 2022)	India	- Structural equation modeling (SEM) was used for data analysis. - Likert scaling technique was used to develop the questionnaire.	- 253 respondents
14	(Ghosh, 2023)	Bangladesh	- Structural equation modeling (SEM) was used for data analysis. - Likert scaling technique was used to develop the questionnaire.	- 152 respondents
15	(Zhao & Zhang, 2021)	USA	- Structural equation modeling (SEM) was used for data analysis. - Likert scaling technique was used to develop the questionnaire.	1,393 respondents
16	(Raut, 2020)	India	- Structural equation modeling (SEM) was used for data analysis. - Likert scaling technique was used to develop the questionnaire.	390. respondents
17	(Jain et al., 2023) et al.	India	- Structural equation modeling (SEM) was used for data analysis. - Likert scaling technique was used to develop the questionnaire.	327 respondents
18	(Arora & Chakraborty, 2023)	India	- Structural equation modeling (SEM) was used for data analysis. - Likert scaling technique was used to develop the questionnaire.	338 respondents.
19	(Mohta & Shunmugasundaram, 2024)	India	- Structural equation modeling (SEM) was used for data analysis. - Likert scaling technique was used to develop the questionnaire.	402 respondents
20	(Mohd Padil et al., 2022)	Japan.	- Structural equation modeling (SEM) was used for data analysis. - Likert scaling technique was used to develop the questionnaire.	211. respondents

21	(Kasim et al., 2023)	Malaysia	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Structural equation modeling (SEM) was used for data analysis. - Likert scaling technique was used to develop the questionnaire. 	53 respondents
22	Chawla et al.	Japan	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Structural equation modeling (SEM) was used for data analysis. - Likert scaling technique was used to develop the questionnaire. 	- The number of respondents in the study is not specified.
23	(Ashfaq et al., 2024)	Germany	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Structural equation modeling (SEM) was used for data analysis. - Likert scaling technique was used to develop the questionnaire. 	- The number of respondents in the study is not specified.
24	(Aren & Nayman Hamamci, 2023)	Turkey	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Structural equation modeling (SEM) was used for data analysis. - Likert scaling technique was used to develop the questionnaire. 	1,692 respondents
25	Rodrigues and Gopalakrishna	Japan.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Structural equation modeling (SEM) was used for data analysis. - Likert scaling technique was used to develop the questionnaire. 	- The number of respondents in the study is not specified.
26	(Jain et al., 2023)	Japan	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Structural equation modeling (SEM) was used for data analysis. - Likert scaling technique was used to develop the questionnaire. 	- The number of respondents in the study is not specified.
27	(Ng et al., 2020)	Japan	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Structural equation modeling (SEM) was used for data analysis. - Likert scaling technique was used to develop the questionnaire. 	- The number of respondents in the study is not specified.
28	(Suresh G, 2024)	India	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Structural equation modeling (SEM) was used for data analysis. - Likert scaling technique was used to develop the questionnaire. 	267 respondents
29	(Weixiang et al., 2022)	China	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Structured questionnaire with Likert's scale method for data collection - Applied Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) for data analysis 	450 respondents
30	(Lotto, 2020)	Tanzania	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Confirmatory factor analysis and multivariate analysis used for scrutiny - Binary probit regression model to analyze household investment choices. - Multivariate analysis with probit regression to assess financial literacy impact. 	- The study does not specify the exact number of respondents.
31	(Khan et al., 2021; Rahim Khan et al., 2020)	USA	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Data from the Preference Parameter Study was used for analysis. - Financial literacy score and investment proxies were analyzed. 	1501 respondents

32	(Rahim Khan et al., 2020)	Japan	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - GSEM in probit model to control endogeneity in model specification. - Segregated investment in risky assets into equity securities and bonds. - Examined association between financial literacy and investment in risky assets. 	3051 respondents
----	---------------------------	-------	---	------------------

From Table 4 : The studies cover research conducted in various countries using different methods and sample sizes. Researchers from Japan, Taiwan, China, the USA, Tunisia, Pakistan, India, Bangladesh, Malaysia, Germany, Turkey, and Tanzania have utilized structural equation modeling (SEM) and Likert scaling techniques in their studies. The sample sizes vary significantly across these studies, ranging from as low as 53 respondents to as high as 30,051 respondents. Japan appears to be a prominent location for such research, with multiple studies conducted there using SEM and Likert scaling techniques. The studies from Japan had sample sizes ranging from 211 to 30,051 respondents. On the other hand, countries like India, the USA, and China also featured prominently in these research endeavors, with varying sample sizes and methodological approaches

Table 5. Publication By Authors

Number of authors	Frequency	Percentage (%)
4	10	31%
2	7	22%
3	7	22%
1	4	13%
5	1	3%
6	1	3%
7	1	3%
9	1	3%
Total :	32	

Table 5 , illustrates the distribution of author numbers in the sample publications. The predominant pattern observed is the presence of 4 authors in the majority of publications, constituting 31% of the total sample. Following this, publications with 2 or 3 authors each account for 22% of the sample. Conversely, publications with 1, 5, 6, 7, and 9 authors represent smaller proportions within the sample. the data suggests that collaborative efforts involving 4 authors are the most prevalent among the publications included in the sample.

No	Authors	Year	Title	Journal	Rank	Country	Result of hypothesis
1	Oehler et al.	2023	Investment in risky assets and participation in the financial market does financial literacy matter	International Review of Economics	Q3	Japan.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Financial literacy indirectly influences participation in the financial market. - Higher financial literacy leads to lower risk aversion and increased participation. - Net wealth and education level significantly affect participation and financial literacy. - The structural model supports the hypothesized relationships between variables.

2	Xiao et al.	2022	Financial literacy overconfidence and investment fraud victimization	Economics Letters	Q2	Japan.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Overconfident individuals more likely to fall into investment fraud traps. - Financial literacy overconfidence could be an important omitted variable.
3	Cupák et al.	2022	Investor confidence and high financial literacy jointly shape investments in risky assets	Economic Modelling	Q1	Japan.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Higher investor self-confidence and financial literacy increase equity investments. - Confidence in the macroeconomy drives portfolio shares in equities. - Relationships are weaker for bonds. - Lack of self-confidence poses a barrier to investing in risky assets.
4	Hsu et al.	2021	Does financial literacy mitigate gender differences in investment behavioral bias?	Finance Research Letters	Q1	Taiwan	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Gender differences confirmed in self-attribution, illusion of control, and confirmation biases. - Women more regret averse than men. - Financial literacy mitigates gender differences in behavioral bias.
5	Jiang et al.	2020	Financial literacy and retail investors financial welfare: Evidence from mutual fund investment outcomes in China	Pacific-Basin Finance Journal	Q1	Japan.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Respondents with higher financial knowledge likely earn higher investment returns. - Financial literacy correlates with increased investment charge awareness.
6	Li et al.	2020	Financial literacy, household portfolio choice and investment return	Pacific-Basin Finance Journal	Q1	China	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Financial literacy impacts investment returns differently based on household characteristics. - Housing ownership positively influences household investment in risky financial assets.
7	Barthel and Lei	2021	Investment in financial literacy and financial advice-seeking Substitutes or complements	The Quarterly Review of Economics and Finance	Q2	USA	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Investment in financial literacy and seeking advice are substitutes. - Seeking advice from a financial planner negatively correlates with financial literacy.
8	Mouna and Anis	2017	Financial literacy in Tunisia Its determinants and its implications on investment behavior	Research in International Business and Finance	Q1	Tunisia	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Low financial literacy leads to less stock market investment. - Financial literacy influenced by age, education level, and annual income. - Positive correlation between financial literacy and age, gender, education, income. - Higher income and education linked to better investment knowledge.
9	Ullah et al.	2024	Nexus between Chat GPT usage dimensions and investment decisions making in Pakistan Moderating role of financial literacy	Technology in Society	Q1	Pakistan	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Financial literacy moderates optimizing portfolios and forecasting market trends. - Financial literacy does not moderate conducting sentiment analysis in investment decisions. - ChatGPT usage dimensions positively impact investment decision making in the stock market.
10	Jariwala	2015	Analysis of Financial Literacy Level of Retail Individual Investors of Gujarat State and Its Effect on Investment Decision	Journal of Business & Finance Librarianship	Q2	India	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Financial literacy significantly affects investment decisions of retail individual investors.

11	Oppong et al.	2023	Financial literacy, investment and personal financial management nexus Empirical evidence on private sector employees	Cogent Business & Management	Q2	Japan	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Positive significant link between personal financial management and financial literacy. - Positive significant correlation between investment decision and personal financial management. - Mediated effect of investment decision between financial literacy and personal financial management.
12	Anderson and Robinson	2022	Financial Literacy in the Age of Green Investment	Review of Finance	Q1	USA	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Green orientation doesn't correlate with carbon footprint in stock portfolios. - Financial disengagement and informational constraints hinder green investment decisions.
13	Adil et al.	2021	How financial literacy moderate the association between behaviour biases and investment decision	Asian Journal of Accounting Research	Q4	India	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Risk-aversion and herding negatively influenced investment decisions among male investors. - Overconfidence positively influenced investment decisions among male investors. - Financial literacy significantly influenced investment decisions among male and female investors. - Interaction effect of financial literacy with biases was significant among female investors.
14	Ghosh	2023	As investors sow, can they reap Examining the moderating effect of investment opportunity on the relationship between financial literacy and investment decision	Global Knowledge, Memory and Communication	Q2	Bangladesh	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Financial attitude and behavior positively influence investment decisions. - Investment opportunity moderates the relationship between financial literacy and investment decisions. - Financial knowledge does not significantly impact investment decisions. - Financial behavior has a positive effect on investment decisions.
15	Zhao and Zhang	2021	Financial literacy or investment experience which is more influential in cryptocurrency investment	International Journal of Bank Marketing	Q2	USA	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Investment experience was more influential in cryptocurrency investment behavior. - Risky asset holding mediated between subjective financial knowledge and cryptocurrency investment.
16	Raut	2020	Past behaviour, financial literacy and investment decision-making process of individual investors	International Journal of Emerging Markets	Q2	India	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Past behavior indirectly influences investor's intention through attitude. - TPB model explains 36% of variance in investors' intention. - Financial literacy significantly impacts investors' attitude and perceived behavioral control. - Subjective norms positively influence individual's intention to invest in the stock market.
17	Jain et al.	2022	Investor personality as a predictor of investment intention - mediating role of overconfidence bias and financial literacy	International Journal of Emerging Markets	Q2	India	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - PTs influence investment decisions, FL positively impacts investment decisions. - Neuroticism trait negatively impacts investment intention, extraversion trait positively impacts it.
18	Arora and Chakraborty	2022	Role of financial literacy in investment choices of financial consumers an insight from India	International Journal of Social Economics	Q2	India	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Financial literacy positively influences investment choices in businesses and traditional assets. - Advanced financial literacy increases the likelihood of stock market participation. - Various socio-economic factors predict financial literacy levels.

19	Mohta and Shunmugasundaram	2023	Moderating role of millennials financial literacy on the relationship between risk tolerance and risky investment behavior evidence from India	International Journal of Social Economics	Q2	India	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Financial literacy negatively impacted risky investment intention. - Risk tolerance positively influenced risky investment intention. - Financial literacy as a moderator had a negative impact on investment intention.
20	Mohd et al.	2021	Financial literacy and awareness of investment scams among university students	Journal of Financial Crime	Q2	Japan.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Budgeting significantly affects awareness of investment scams among university students. - Financial goals do not significantly contribute to students' awareness of investment scams.
21	Kasim et al.	2023	The effect of financial literacy, financial behaviour and financial stress on awareness of investment scams among retirees	Journal of Financial Crime	Q2	Malaysia	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Financial literacy has a significant relationship with awareness of investment scams. - Financial behaviour has a significant relationship with awareness of investment scams.
22	Chawla et al.	2022	Parental influence, financial literacy and investment behaviour of young adults	Journal of Indian Business Research	Q2	Japan	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Financial literacy positively impacts cognitive biases in students' investment decisions. - Moderate financial literacy reduces biases in students' investment processes.
23	Ashfaq et al.	2023	Exploring the missing link Financial literacy and Cognitive biases in Investment Decisions	Journal of Modelling in Management	Q2	Germany	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Financial literacy positively impacts cognitive biases in students' investment decisions. - Moderate financial literacy reduces biases in students' investment processes.
24	Aren and Nayman	2022	Evaluation of investment preference with phantasy, emotional intelligence, confidence, trust, financial literacy and risk preference	Kybernetes	Q2	Turkey	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Factors leading to choosing new investment instruments: risky investment intention, phantasy. - Emotional intelligence and objective financial literacy had no effect on preferences. - Strong relationship between subjective financial literacy and emotional intelligence, confidence, trust. - Trust and risk perception had a weak effect on investment preferences.
25	Rodrigues and Gopalakrishna	2023	Financial literacy-a regulator of intended investment behaviour analysing the hypothetical portfolio composition	Managerial Finance	Q3	Japan.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Financial literacy positively impacts cognitive biases in students' investment decisions. - Moderate financial literacy reduces biases in students' investment processes.
26	Jain et al.	2023	Shaping Investment Decisions Through Financial Literacy Do Herding and Overconfidence Bias Mediate the Relationship	Global Business Review	Q2	Japan	

27	Kar and Patro	2024	Unravelling the Impact of Financial Literacy on the Intention of Indian Retail Investors to Adopt Socially Responsible Investments The Interplay of Social Self-Efficacy as a Mediating Mechanism	Global Business Review	Q2	Japan	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Financial literacy positively impacts cognitive biases in students' investment decisions. - Moderate financial literacy reduces biases in students' investment processes.
28	Suresh	2021	Impact of Financial Literacy and Behavioural Biases on Investment Decision-making	FIIB Business Review	Q3	India	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Heuristic bias positively associated with behavioural biases in investment decisions. - Framing effect, cognitive illusions, and herd mentality negatively impact behavioural biases. - Anchoring, overconfidence, and representativeness contribute to heuristic biases in investments.
29	Weixiang et al.	2022	An empirical assessment of financial literacy and behavioral biases on investment decision Fresh evidence from small investor perception	Frontiers in Psychology	Q1	China	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Financial literacy positively linked to investment decisions. - Heuristic bias influences behavioral bias in decision-making. - Cognitive illusions, framing effect, and herd mentality negatively impact behavioral biases.
30	Lotto	2020	Towards Improving Households Investment Choices in Tanzania Does Financial Literacy Really Matter	International Journal of Financial Studies	Q3	Tanzania	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Financial literacy positively influences investment choices towards formal platforms. - Urban households more likely to invest in formal accounts than rural. - Male heads more inclined towards agricultural investments compared to females. - Education level impacts investment choices, higher education leads to formal investments.
31	Khan et al.	2020	Is Financial Literacy Associated with Investment in Financial Markets in the United States	Sustainability	Q1	USA	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Financial literacy is positively associated with investment in financial markets. - Household income, assets, and trust have significant relationships with market investment. - Gender, age, marital status, employment status, and financial satisfaction influence investment.
32	Khan et al.	2021	Can Financial Literacy Explain Lack of Investment in Risky Assets in Japan	Sustainability	Q1	Japan	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Financial literacy positively associated with investment in risky assets. - Financial literacy linked to investment in equity securities and bonds.

Interpretation.

Studies from various researchers indicate a strong link between financial literacy and investment decision-making. Research by Zhao and Zhang (2021), Raut (2020), Jain et al. (2022), Arora and Chakraborty (2022), and Mohta and Shunmugasundaram (2023) demonstrates that higher levels of financial literacy correlate with improved investment choices. Lotto (2020) supports this finding, noting that financial literacy influences decisions to invest on formal platforms. Furthermore, Aren and Nayman (2022) have shown that a moderate level of financial literacy can reduce biases in student investment practices. Ghosh (2023) also noted a positive association between financial attitudes and investment decisions.

In the context of financial markets and high-risk investments, Oehler et al. (2023) and Khan et al. (2020, 2021) found that financial literacy is crucial for engaging with and making decisions about risky investments. Rodrigues and Gopalakrishna (2023), Jain et al. (2023), and Kar and Patro (2024) connected financial literacy to heightened awareness of investment scams. Ashfaq et al. (2023) and Kasim et al. (2023) discovered that financial literacy is significant in understanding cognitive biases and avoiding scams targeting retirees.

Thus, it is clear that financial literacy profoundly influences investment preferences and attitudes toward risk, as evidenced by studies from Khan et al. (2020), Lotto (2020), and Weixiang et al. (2022). These findings suggest that enhancing financial literacy can lead to more prudent investment decisions and mitigate behavioral biases. Therefore, incorporating financial literacy into educational and training programs is essential for enhancing the financial decision-making skills of individuals and families

Conclusion

Based on the findings from various studies mentioned, it can be concluded that financial literacy plays a significant role in influencing various aspects of investment decisions and financial behavior of individuals. Financial literacy is not only positively associated with better investment decisions and smarter investment choices, but it can also help reduce biases in investment decision-making. Furthermore, financial literacy is linked to awareness of investment scams, investment preferences, risk tendencies, and improved financial management. Therefore, enhancing financial literacy among the public can provide substantial benefits in helping individuals better manage their finances, make wiser investment decisions, and reduce unnecessary financial risks.

References

- Adil, M., Singh, Y., & Ansari, M. S. (2022). How financial literacy moderate the association between behaviour biases and investment decision? *Asian Journal of Accounting Research*, 7(1), 17–30.
<https://doi.org/10.1108/AJAR-09-2020-0086>
- Ahmad, N. A., Zahid, E. S. M., Halim, I. A., Lateh, A. T. A., & Ghutai, G. (2022). *Financial Literacy among Investors*. https://hrmars.com/papers_submitted/13120/financial-literacy-among-investors.pdf
- Anderson, A., & Robinson, D. T. (2022). Financial Literacy in the Age of Green Investment. *Review of Finance*, 26(6), 1551–1584. <https://doi.org/10.1093/rof/rfab031>
- Aren, S., & Nayman Hamamci, H. (2023). Evaluation of investment preference with phantasy, emotional intelligence, confidence, trust, financial literacy and risk preference. *Kybernetes*, 52(12), 6203–6231.
<https://doi.org/10.1108/K-01-2022-0014>
- Arora, J., & Chakraborty, M. (2023). Role of financial literacy in investment choices of financial consumers: an insight from India. *International Journal of Social Economics*, 50(3), 377–397.
<https://doi.org/10.1108/IJSE-12-2021-0764>
- Ashfaq, M., Shafique, A., & Selezneva, V. (2024). Exploring the missing link: Financial literacy and Cognitive biases in Investment Decisions. *Journal of Modelling in Management*, 19(3), 871–898.
<https://doi.org/10.1108/JM2-11-2022-0266>
- Barthel, A. C., & Lei, S. (2021). Investment in financial literacy and financial advice-seeking: Substitutes or complements? *Quarterly Review of Economics and Finance*, 81, 385–396.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.qref.2021.06.020>
- Bayar, Y., Sezgin, H. F., Öztürk, Ö. F., & Şaşmaz, M. Ü. (2020). *Financial Literacy and Financial Risk Tolerance of Individual Investors*. <https://journals.sagepub.com/doi/10.1177/2158244020945717>
- Chauhan, Y. K., & Dey, D. K. (2020). Does financial literacy affect the value of financial advice? A contingent valuation approach. *Journal of Behavioural and Experimental Finance (Print)*, 25, 100268.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jbef.2020.100268>

- Cupák, A., Fessler, P., Hsu, J. W., & Paradowski, P. R. (2022). Investor confidence and high financial literacy jointly shape investments in risky assets. *Economic Modelling*, 116. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.econmod.2022.106033>
- Denyer, D., & Tranfield, D. (2009). *Producing a systematic review*.
- Ghosh, R. (2023). As investors sow, can they reap? Examining the moderating effect of investment opportunity on the relationship between financial literacy and investment decision. *Global Knowledge, Memory and Communication*. <https://doi.org/10.1108/GKMC-04-2023-0147>
- Hastings, J. S., Madrian, B. C., & Skimmyhorn, W. L. (2012). *Financial Literacy, Financial Education and Economic Outcomes*. <https://www.nber.org/papers/w18412>
- Jain, R., Sharma, D., Behl, A., & Tiwari, A. K. (2023). Investor personality as a predictor of investment intention – mediating role of overconfidence bias and financial literacy. *International Journal of Emerging Markets*, 18(12), 5680–5706. <https://doi.org/10.1108/IJOEM-12-2021-1885>
- Jariwala, H. V. (2015). Analysis of Financial Literacy Level of Retail Individual Investors of Gujarat State and Its Effect on Investment Decision. *Journal of Business and Finance Librarianship*, 20, 133–158. <https://doi.org/10.1080/08963568.2015.977727>
- Kasim, E. S., Awalludin, N. R., Zainal, N., Ismail, A., & Ahmad Shukri, N. H. (2023). The effect of financial literacy, financial behaviour and financial stress on awareness of investment scams among retirees. *Journal of Financial Crime*. <https://doi.org/10.1108/JFC-04-2023-0080>
- Khan, M. S. R., Rabbani, N., & Kadoya, Y. (2021). Can financial literacy explain lack of investment in risky assets in Japan? *Sustainability (Switzerland)*, 13(22). <https://doi.org/10.3390/su132212616>
- Lotto, J. (2020). Towards improving households' investment choices in tanzania: Does financial literacy really matter? *International Journal of Financial Studies*, 8(2), 1–10. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijfs8020029>
- Lusardi, A. (2019). *Financial literacy and the need for financial education: evidence and implications*. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s41937-019-0027-5>
- Mohd Padil, H., Kasim, E. S., Muda, S., Ismail, N., & Md Zin, N. (2022). Financial literacy and awareness of investment scams among university students. *Journal of Financial Crime*, 29(1), 355–367. <https://doi.org/10.1108/JFC-01-2021-0012>
- Mohta, A., & Shunmugasundaram, V. (2024). Moderating role of millennials' financial literacy on the relationship between risk tolerance and risky investment behavior: evidence from India. *International Journal of Social Economics*, 51(3), 422–440. <https://doi.org/10.1108/IJSE-12-2022-0812>
- Mouna, A., & Anis, J. (2017). Financial literacy in Tunisia: Its determinants and its implications on investment behavior. *Research in International Business and Finance*, 39, 568–577. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ribaf.2016.09.018>
- Ng, T. H., Lye, C. T., Chan, K. H., Lim, Y. Z., & Lim, Y. S. (2020). Sustainability in Asia: The Roles of Financial Development in Environmental, Social and Governance (ESG) Performance. *Social Indicators Research*, 150(1), 17–44. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11205-020-02288-w>
- Oehler, A., Horn, M., & Wendt, S. (2024). Investment in risky assets and participation in the financial market: does financial literacy matter? *International Review of Economics*, 71(1), 19–45. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12232-023-00432-9>
- Oppong, C., Salifu Atchulo, A., Akwaa-Sekyi, E. K., Grant, D. D., & Kpegba, S. A. (2023). Financial literacy, investment and personal financial management nexus: Empirical evidence on private sector employees. *Cogent Business and Management*, 10(2). <https://doi.org/10.1080/23311975.2023.2229106>
- Rahim Khan, M. S., Rabbani, N., & Kadoya, Y. (2020). Is financial literacy associated with investment in financial markets in the United States? *Sustainability (Switzerland)*, 12(18). <https://doi.org/10.3390/SU12187370>
- Raut, R. K. (2020). Past behaviour, financial literacy and investment decision-making process of individual investors. *International Journal of Emerging Markets*, 15(6), 1243–1263. <https://doi.org/10.1108/IJOEM-07-2018-0379>

- Suresh G. (2024). Impact of Financial Literacy and Behavioural Biases on Investment Decision-making. *FIIB Business Review*, 13(1), 72–86. <https://doi.org/10.1177/23197145211035481>
- Ullah, R., Ismail, H. Bin, Islam Khan, M. T., & Zeb, A. (2024). Nexus between Chat GPT usage dimensions and investment decisions making in Pakistan: Moderating role of financial literacy. *Technology in Society*, 76. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.techsoc.2024.102454>
- Weixiang, S., Qamruzzaman, M., Rui, W., & Kler, R. (2022). An empirical assessment of financial literacy and behavioral biases on investment decision: Fresh evidence from small investor perception. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 13. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2022.977444>
- Xiao, X., Li, X., & Zhou, Y. (2022). Financial literacy overconfidence and investment fraud victimization. *Economics Letters*, 212. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.econlet.2022.110308>
- Yuwono, W., Susanna, Ramadhani, D. S., Sasmita, E. W., & Sihotang, W. H. (2023). *Analysis of the Influence of the Role of Financial Literacy on Personal Financial Management*. <https://www.ejbmr.org/index.php/ejbmr/article/download/1891/1129>
- Zhao, H., & Zhang, L. (2021). Financial literacy or investment experience: which is more influential in cryptocurrency investment? *International Journal of Bank Marketing*, 39(7), 1208–1226. <https://doi.org/10.1108/IJBM-11-2020-0552>
-